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INCREASE EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY AND AUTOMATION THROUGH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract: Generative artificial intelligence does not completely take over someone's work and "destroy" jobs, but rather automates certain tasks. Socio-economic consequences of the development of generative artificial intelligence, the opinion of workers, their preparation and sufficient social protection to manage such a process are described in this article.

Keywords: Preetpal Singh, SVP, AI, IOM, Hyperautomation, ML, KPI ERP, AI, HR.

The rapid development of artificial intelligence in recent years can be attributed to several key factors, including increased available bandwidth, improved computing speed, widespread use of cloud computing, and advances in programming. These factors have created a synergistic environment that encourages the development and adoption of artificial intelligence. Most jobs and industries are only partially automated. At the same time, the functionality of such workers is more likely to be supplemented by the spread of generative artificial intelligence, such as ChatGPT.

The scope and use of artificial intelligence has grown dramatically over the past decade, paving the way for the HR department to do its job. Keeping pace with rapid technological advances, artificial intelligence is now helping to simplify everyday problems and critical tasks. It helps HR managers in their day-to-day tasks like recruiting, onboarding, talent management, payroll, and more.

KPI ERP is an AI-powered platform that helps streamline HR processes, enabling organizations to improve operational efficiency, attract and retain the best talent pool, and reduce costs. Organizations are paying a lot of attention to workforce analysis and planning.

Repetitive administrative tasks are the most demanding tasks in any HR department. A lot of correspondence, email follow-ups, filing, managing payroll, managing compliance, scrutinizing

performance review data, and more can be overwhelming. Such repetitive low-level tasks take up a lot of time that would otherwise be used to solve work-related problems.

With KPI ERP, most of these repetitive administrative tasks can be left to the KPI HR management system. Conversations that require perfect accuracy, such as payroll management and compliance, are better handled by a KPI ERP system.

AI-powered platforms such as KPI HRMS have greatly simplified the recruitment cycle by using AI to perform key functions such as skill matching, labor market analysis, identifying inaccuracies in job descriptions and skill identification.

Key features such as resume screening and automation of HR FAQs help to effectively communicate with candidates, reducing a lot of effort and time to work.

AI is becoming more evident in HR systems. AI in HR empowers managers to solve problems and can lead to more informed decisions that impact employee and organizational success. For example, using real-time analytics shows managers the impact of downtime, open shifts, and unplanned schedule changes on key performance indicators, allowing them to make more informed decisions that prevent problems before they happen. With an intuitive and fast HR system like KPI ERP, we simplify and improve HR through artificial intelligence.

AI or artificial intelligence usually refers to the development of computer systems or machines that can perform tasks that require human intelligence. These tasks include problem solving, learning, understanding and natural language processing, pattern recognition, and decision making.

Hyperautomation combines various technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), event-driven software architecture, low-code-no-code (LCNC), intelligent business process management suites (iBPMS), and conversational AI to simplify and automate various business processes. The hyperautomation market is currently valued at approximately \$12.95 billion and is expected to grow to \$31.95 billion by 2029. The main catalyst for this growth is the widespread adoption of digitization on a global scale.

For example, Robotic Process Automation uses software "bots" or "robots" to automate repetitive tasks, ideal because they follow predictable patterns without the need to make complex decisions. One notable application is invoice processing, where hyperautomation can effectively check invoice details, cross-reference and identify discrepancies. The benefits of hyperautomation include cost reduction, increased efficiency, early revenue recognition, and the ability of organizations to leverage data from digitized processes.

Thus, it takes over complex decision-making processes, enables organizations to simplify operations and improve efficiency in various sectors. Using a code-free platform can help companies reduce overall timelines by 60-70 percent. Advanced data analytics capabilities, including automatic summarization, anomaly detection, and predictive maintenance, enable data-driven decision making and proactive risk management.

References

1. Sh.A. Nazirov, M.M. Musaycv, A. Nematov, R.V. Acceptance. Fundamentals of Delphi programming. Tashkent: Publishing House named after Gafur Ghulam. 2007.

2. Sh.A. Nazirov, R.V. Acceptance. Object-oriented programming. — Tashkent: publishing house named after G'ofur G'uloin. 2007.
3. January 19, 2024 "Gazeta News" LLC
4. 2024 DK New Media, LLC.